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GLOBAL PATTERNS OF SOLAR RESOURCE SHORT-TERM VARIABILITY BASED ON SOLARGIS TIME SERIES DATA

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ABSTRACT: The era of modern meteorological satellites provides new opportunities for analysis of variability derived from satellite-based solar resource data. Combining satellite missions together makes it possible to analyse variability on a global scale. This study provides information on the occurrence and magnitude of the short-term solar resource variability, globally. Our approach is based on statistical processing of a 10-minute and 15-minute time series of Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), derived from the Solargis satellite-to-irradiance model data from five satellite missions covering the globe. The analysis is performed for a period of the recent 5 years (2019 – 2023, the era of modern meteorological satellites) in a grid with 4-km nominal spatial resolution. The variability statistics are communicated in the form of graphs and maps. Short term solar resource variability (solar ramp rates) shows strong seasonal and geographical patterns. We analyse the typical size of solar ramp rates and patterns in their temporal and geographical spread. The main advantage of the presented approach is understanding of short-term variability and its changing patterns globally, across regions and seasons, especially where availability of solar meteorological measurements is very limited. Information about the variability is important for planning and development of electrical grids and photovoltaic (PV) projects.

Keywords: solar resource ramps, solar resource variability, sub-hourly variability, global map of variability

1 INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of the short-term variability (intermittency) of solar resource has been explored by several authors in the past. Most often, it is presented in statistical terms, optimally derived from (sub)minute high-quality solar resource ground measurements, or carefully validated PV power production data. However, such analysis is typically valid only locally.

Extrapolation of the variability statistics has rarely been attempted by utilisation of satellite-based solar resource data, cloud-specific products, or climate model data. The studies that utilize these data sources are typically focused on one region only [1], [2], [3]. The era of modern meteorological satellites provides opportunities not available years ago: increased temporal and spatial resolution, improved positional geometry, more spectral bands for enhanced identification of cloud characteristics. Combining satellite missions together makes it possible to analyse variability in a global coverage.

In this study we utilize the solar resource data from the Solargis satellite-based model to derive global indicators of solar resource short-term variability. The global indicators allow comparison or correlation of the intermittency among locations and regions globally. The results should be useful to grid utilities, and PV power plant developers and operators can develop approaches to mitigate the impacts of solar resource intermittency.

2 METHODOLOGY

There are two main drivers of the short-term solar resource variability [4]:

- a) solar geometry, well documented by formulae,
- b) clouds.

Forming or moving clouds cause abrupt changes in solar irradiance within minutes or even seconds, which is also recognized as “solar power ramps” or “ramp rates” [5]. Depending on the type, clouds are capable of consuming a part of the direct irradiance and transforming the rest into diffuse irradiance. Specifically, moving

scattered (intermittent) clouds induce frequent up and down solar resource changes. Developing massive storm clouds or moving frontal clouds with a low base often cause abrupt reduction of solar irradiance. For these reasons, photovoltaic (PV) power generation is sometimes referred to as a variable resource, as it is not stable in time and space. Intermittency of the solar resource poses challenges to the grid stability.

In this study, the short-term variability of solar resource data is based on a statistical analysis of time series of Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI), calculated by the Solargis satellite-based solar model. Data from meteorological satellites, atmospheric models, solar geometry, and terrain are the main inputs into the solar model [6]. One of the model output parameters is a grid of harmonised GHI time series data, available globally.

A subset of the recent 5 years of data (the era of modern meteorological satellites), with nominal spatial resolution of 2 arcmin (nominally 4 km) is considered in this study. The calculation is performed separately for the regions of five satellite missions for the land area between latitudes 60°N and 60°S, with the following calculation step, related to the time step of data acquisition:

- *10-minute* for Americas, Australia, East Asia, and Pacific, covered by the GOES and HIMAWARI satellites, operated by NASA and JMA, respectively
- *15-minute* for Europe, Africa, and West Asia, covered by Meteosat MSG satellites, operated by EUMETSAT.

The source data is then processed in five steps, described below. The processing of the data is performed separately for each satellite region, and the global dataset is merged together in the last step.

Firstly, the solar noon for each day of the year is calculated as a global gridded dataset. An adapted PSA sun position algorithm is used to perform the calculations.

Secondly, Solargis GHI time series data is subset to ± 3 hours from the solar noon. This is the time of the day with a potential for high-magnitude solar power ramp occurrences. In the morning or evening hours GHI has lower magnitude due to low sun angles. For this reason, these time slots are filtered out from further processing (Figure 1).

Thirdly, the differences between the consecutive time slots are calculated. The calculation is done for each day of the month, season, or year for every grid cell, globally (Figure 2). In this way, a time series of GHI differences is calculated, covering 6 hours every day within the considered time period (2019 – 2023). This global gridded dataset is the basis for the statistical evaluation of the short-term variability.

Fourthly, relevant statistics are calculated to describe different aspects of the short-term variability. The calculated statistics include standard deviation of the GHI difference time series, extreme percentile values (P90, P99), and counts of exceedance occurrences of certain thresholds.

Lastly, the data for the five satellite regions is merged into a single seamless global dataset, and the relevant statistical array data are selected and presented as cartographical outputs. The cartographical outputs can then be investigated and interpreted to understand the regional characteristics of global short-term variability of solar resource data.

Figure 1: Example of the sub-setting of GHI time series data at a single location: GHI 15-minute time series for ± 3 hours from the solar noon for all days in June 2023 in Vienna

Figure 2: Calculated differences from consecutive 15-minute time slots for all 31 days in June 2023 for the same location as in Figure 1

2.1 Limitations of data from satellite-based solar models compared to ground measurements

It is evident that the variability of solar resource can be large under specific synoptic scenarios, as seen in high-frequency good quality ground measurements. Magnitude and occurrence of ramps in ground-based pyranometer measurements at 1-minute time step can be much higher (even multiple times) compared to the variability observed in time series data with 10- or 15-minute time step (from a pyranometer or satellite-based models). An example of this difference is shown in Figure 3, comparing 1-minute

ground measurements, and 10-minute, 15-minute, and hourly data derived from Solargis time series.

Figure 3: Screenshots from Solargis Analyst software. Comparison of GHI time series of different temporal resolutions for a location in Central Highlands, Vietnam; 1-min derived from ground data measured from ESMAP solar meteorological stations network, station VNCEH [7], [8]. 10-minute, 15-minute and hourly derived from Solargis Time Series

On the other hand, the variability of the power output of a utility-scale PV power plant will be lower than that in pyranometer measurements. This is due to the so-called spatial averaging effect. As the power plant integrates solar resource over its whole area into the power output, the variability of the output will represent the average irradiation over the whole plant. The effect is stronger the larger the powerplant is.

Figure 4: Distribution of the pyranometers in Freiburg (data from [9]), their grouping for the variability analysis, and size of a satellite pixel. (Map background source: © OpenStreetMap contributors)

An analysis of ground-measured data [9] from 6 pyranometers located in Freiburg, Germany demonstrates the spatial averaging effect. The distribution of the sites is shown in Figure 4. As shown in Figure 5, the variability of the individual point measurements with 1-minute time resolution is significantly larger than that of the 15-minute Solargis satellite model time series of GHI. However, when the measured GHI is averaged for 2, 3, and all 6 pyranometers, the resultant variability of the 1-minute time series is comparable to the variability of the 15-minute Solargis data. The variability is measured as the number of ramps over a certain size in one year of data. The distance between the 2 and 3 grouped sites is approximately 1 km and 3 km respectively, which is comparable to the size of a utility-scale PV power plant. Noting the limited geographical context, the analysis indicates that the variability derived from the 15-minute

satellite-based model GHI data is a practical proxy for assessing the variability of the power output of a typical large-scale PV power plant.

Figure 5: Variability of the measured 1-minute time series data [9], aggregations of the measured data, and Solargis 15-minute satellite model time series

3 RESULTS

In this chapter the resultant maps are analysed and the observed patterns described to understand the characteristics of short-term variability of solar resource in world regions.

3.1 Patterns of solar resource variability

Figure 6 shows the standard deviation of the differences between the consecutive GHI timestamps in the recent five years. The maps are split according to seasons (Dec – Feb, Mar – May, Jun – Aug, Sep – Nov) to identify regional patterns. We provide a short analysis of the likely sources of the observed patterns, however, a more detailed work is needed to provide conclusive explanations.

High variability in all seasons is observed in regions of equatorial Africa, Indonesia, Papua New Guinea, in a belt from Northern Amazonia, through Central American countries, up to the Yucatan peninsula in Mexico. Similar ramp magnitudes are found in the northeast coast of Madagascar. These areas are consistent with occurrence of broken clouds in the tropical regions, which are typically the main cause of solar resource variability.

High variability in two or three seasons, low in one season is observed in regions of Southern Africa, Australia and over large territories of Latin America. These areas experience more stable solar resource during their winter period.

Medium variability with seasonal spikes, is observed e.g., in South India, Southeast Somalia, coastal parts of Kenya, Yemen, Western Europe, or Northwest Iran. Many phenomena with regional impact could be the cause of these patterns, including monsoon and the occurrence of the rainy season in the tropics.

Zonal character of variability, includes interesting patterns in North America or Europe, requiring deeper analysis to offer proper interpretation

Low variability in all seasons, observed in the southeast part of the Sahara Desert, Northeast China (most of Xinjiang province) or in the central part of continental Russia. These areas have either arid or strongly continental climate, which could be expected to lead to low occurrence of weather variations leading to cloud formation.

Figure 6: Seasonal indicator of the short-term solar resource variability, calculated as standard deviation from Solargis 10-minute and 15-minute GHI ramps calculated for a subset ± 3 hours around the solar noon for a period 2019 to 2023.

3.2 Occurrence of large solar ramps

Figure 7 presents the average annual number of solar ramp rates exceeding defined thresholds, calculated from the Solargis time series. We summarise the number of occurrences in a typical year, when a GHI ramp is larger than 500 W/m², 400 W/m² or 300 W/m², within a 10-minute or 15-minute interval (interval depends on the satellite region).

From this perspective we identify the most apparent solar resource ramps in the northeast coastal regions of Latin America, and some parts of Central America. Here we find areas where the solar resource ramp (rise or drop) of the magnitude 500 W/m² is documented more than 360 times in an average year (or once a day on average), and the 300 W/m² ramp far beyond 1000 times in an typical year (on average 3 to 4 times a day).

The other regions with frequent solar ramps include coastal regions of Australia (with the exception of the West coast), most of the islands in Southeast Asia, high mountains and surrounding plateaus in central Asia, northeast coast of Madagascar, southeast coastal regions of Somalia, and coastal areas in the Gulf of Guinea. Low occurrence of the abrupt solar power ramps is seen in Northeast Africa, central North Asia (Northeast China, Russia) or Northwest Canada.

The patterns correlate with the statistics presented in Figure 6. Some regions deserve further analysis on a

regional scale, e.g. we see strong regional variations in China, Australia, USA, but also other regions.

Figure 7: Average annual number of GHI ramps calculated from Solargis 10-minute and 15-minute time series consecutive differences during the day-time ± 3 hours around the solar noon in the period 2019 to 2023, exceeding the magnitude 500 W/m², 400 W/m² and 300 W/m²

4 DISCUSSION

Solar resource ramps, determined by changing and moving clouds, pose a challenge for management of electric grids and smooth PV electricity supply. In this study we calculated metrics for evaluation of short-term solar resource variability based on Solargis satellite model-based data, and produced world maps of these indicators to study the patterns of the short-term variability. We classify world regions based on the magnitude and occurrence GHI short-term variability, and show the variation of the solar ramps over seasons.

The data and maps can be helpful for strategic planning of electrical grids and PV assets. Specifically, in the high variability areas, the impact of PV power generation on the grid should be carefully analysed, supported by high-quality ground measurements. Adequate dispersion of the PV power plants in a region enables geographical smoothing of the aggregated PV power generation curve. However, to enable this geographical smoothing effect, transmission capacity in the region must be sufficient to support the necessary balancing power flows. Areas with high intermittency are also the best candidates for development of short-term energy storage, capable of providing the balancing power and smoothing the PV power generation curve.

Furthermore, the forecast of PV power, but also historical solar models, has a higher uncertainty in the regions during the seasons with high short-term solar

resource variability. Predictability of solar irradiance specifically in regions with frequent intermittent clouds is much more complex than in the regions with prevailing clear-sky or overcast days. This should be reflected in the uncertainty of forecast or historical data, and considered by the users of the data in their further interpretation, including financial models.

Ongoing improvements in satellite-based models and computing infrastructure will make it possible to process data with very high frequency (2.5- and 5-minute frequency of data acquisition) and higher grid resolution (starting at 500 metres). New solar resource models being designed for time series data with high time resolution (1 to 15 minutes) have the potential to support an improved analysis of short-term solar resource variability. In regions with frequent occurrence of large solar ramps, this will make it possible to prepare better technical designs of hybrid PV systems and make the operation of electrical grids more robust.

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